

(27°) using solutions containing 6 mg sample in 2.5 ml CDCl_3 containing 0.03% TMS as internal standard.

Results and Discussion

The ^{13}C nmr chemical shifts of methoxy carbons and methylthio carbons (Table 1) offer an interesting study. The conjugation of CH_3O with electron-attracting groups like NO_2 and COCH_3 should be

TABLE 1— ^{13}C NMR CHEMICAL SHIFTS (ppm) OF METHOXY CARBONS OF ANISOLES AND METHYLTHIO CARBONS OF THIOANISOLES

Anisole		Thioanisole	
4-Substituent	OCH_3	4-Substituent	SCH_3
Nil	55.1	Nil	15.8 ^a
NO_2	58.0	NO_2	14.9 ^b
COCH_3	55.5	COCH_3	14.8
NH_2	55.7	NH_2	18.3
OCH_3	55.8	OCH_3	18.1 ^c
F	55.4	F	17.1 ^d
Cl	55.0	Cl	18.1 ^d
Br	55.1	Br	16.1 ^d
I	55.2	—	—

Literature values (Ref. 1): ^a15.9, ^b15.0, ^c17.9, ^dValue from Ref. 1.

C-13 Nmr Chemical Shifts of Methoxy Carbon in Anisoles and Methylthio Carbon in Thioanisoles

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A comparative study of organosulphur compounds and their oxygen analogues with respect to their physical and chemical properties is of considerable interest. This study presents a comparative analysis of the ^{13}C nmr chemical shifts of CH_3O in anisoles and CH_3S in thioanisoles.

Experimental

Some of the compounds examined were commercially available and the others were prepared by literature methods. They were purified before use.

The ^{13}C nmr spectra were determined on a JEOL FX 90Q spectrometer (90 MHz) at room temperature

expected to cause a downfield shift of the methoxy carbon because the electron-withdrawal from the methoxy oxygen imparts a positive charge to the oxygen and this in turn makes the methoxy carbon acquire a positive charge. What is observed is in accordance with the expectation. Surprisingly, the conjugation of the same electron-withdrawing groups, NO_2 and COCH_3 with CH_3S produces an opposite effect in thioanisole. The shift of the methylthio carbon resonance is upfield and not downfield. The reason for this becomes clear if one bears in mind the factors which cause upfield and downfield shifts. An upfield shift results when the concerned carbon atom acquires increased electron density or experiences shielding by other atoms or groups. The downfield shift results with decreased electron density or with decreased shielding. In anisole molecule the methoxy group tends to attain coplanarity with the benzene ring² due to its resonance with the ring, leading to its being shielded by the benzene ring. If the shielding gets increased due to any reason, the methoxy carbon shows an upfield shift. That is what happened to methylthio carbons in 4-nitrothioanisole and 4-acetylthioanisole.

The CH_3S conjugates with NO_2 as in 1 and the CH_3O as in 2. The involvement of the CH_3 of CH_3S in hyperconjugation makes the free

rotation of CH_3S more restricted and it becomes more coplanar with the benzene ring than CH_3O and the

methylthio carbon experiences greater shielding. Furthermore, the existence of positive charge on oxygen in 2 and the absence of it on sulphur in 1 makes the methoxy carbon in 2 to have a lower electron density. There is evidence for the resonance of thioanisole as in 3, involving hyperconjugation of CH_3 . Anisole undergoes nuclear

metallation, while under the same conditions, thioanisole undergoes lateral metallation³, indicating that the hydrogens of CH_3S are labile. The methylene group of arylomercaptopropionic acids is more reactive than that of aryloacetic acids⁴ showing the importance of resonance structures of the type 4, sulphur becoming tetravalent utilising the vacant d -orbitals in its valence shell. The dissociation constants of p -methyl-, p -ethyl- and p -isopropylmercaptobenzoic acids show that the dissociation constant increases in the order: isopropyl > ethyl > methyl, indicating the valence shell expansion of sulphur and involvement of hyperconjugation⁵.

The methoxy carbon chemical shifts of 4-aminoanisole and 4-methoxyanisole as well as the methylthio carbon chemical shifts of 4-aminothioanisole and 4-methoxythioanisole are downfield compared to those of anisole and thioanisole, respectively. The methoxy carbons of both 4-nitroanisole and 4-aminoanisole, with polar substituents of opposite nature, having downfield shifts may appear perplexing at first sight. However, they become understandable after proper analysis.

In 4-aminoanisole and 4-methoxyanisole the electron-releasing methoxy group is opposed by another electron-releasing group with the result its freedom to be out of the plane of the benzene ring compared to that in anisole increases and its carbon is deshielded. Thus the methoxy carbon chemical shift in anisole is 55.1 ppm and the same in 4-methoxyaniline and 4-methoxyanisole is higher (55.7 and 55.8 ppm, respectively).

In 4-aminothioanisole and 4-methoxythioanisole the CH_3S conjugates with electron-releasing groups NH_2 and OCH_3 , respectively, as shown in 6 and 7. Here sulphur becomes an electron-acceptor expanding its valence shell with the utilisation of the vacant d -orbitals. There is ample evidence for the

CH_3S group functioning as an electron acceptor^{6,7}. A group involved in d -orbital resonance need not be coplanar with the benzene ring for effective $3d-2p$ π -bonding⁷. The out-of-plane CH_3S experiences less shielding by the benzene ring and the methylthio carbon resonates downfield.

In Table 1 are also given the methoxy carbon chemical shifts of p -halogenoanisoles and p -halogeno-thioanisoles. The F substituent, with its appreciable $+M$ effect (substituent parameter p , -4.5)⁸, shows the expected downfield shift in both 4-fluoroanisole and 4-fluorothioanisole. The $+M$ effect of Cl and Br is feeble and I has even $-M$ effect (substituent parameters⁸: Cl p , -1.9 ; Br p , -1.6 ; I p , $+1.0$). So the observed methoxy carbon chemical shifts of the chloro and bromo compounds are also in the expected range.

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